

**DESIGN AND PRACTICAL OPERATION OF SIMPLIFIED REGISTRATION AND
COLLECTION REGIMES****Ashir Shah Hotak****Termez davlat universiteti****Telfon-+93 79 493 2560A**

Abstract: In January 2021, the OECD Committee on Fiscal Affairs (CFA) requested the development of guidance to support the coherent implementation of the International VAT/GST Guidelines (the Guidelines) as incorporated in the OECD Council Recommendation on the Application of Value Added Tax/Goods and Services Tax to the International Trade in Services and Intangibles [C(2021)120]1. This work is expected to result in a series of reports providing practical guidance to tax authorities, to facilitate the effective and coherent implementation of the principles of the Guidelines, thereby taking into account differences in jurisdictions' legislative framework and administrative capacity. This work is carried out by the OECD's Working Party No 9 on Consumption Taxes (WP9), in close consultation with the business community through the Technical Advisory Group to WP9 (TAG). The CFA requested that WP9 focus first on the development of concrete guidance for the design and practical implementation of mechanisms for the efficient and effective collection of VAT/GST on supplies of services and intangibles by foreign suppliers, as recommended in the Guidelines. The outcome of this work is presented in this report (hereafter the "report on collection mechanisms").

key wrd: greater, collection, introduction, registration, practical, vat/gst, oecd

Introduction

The Guidelines recommend that, "When implementing a registration-based collection mechanism, jurisdictions consider establishing a simplified registration and compliance regime to facilitate compliance for non-resident suppliers".¹ The highest feasible levels of compliance by foreign suppliers are likely to be achieved if compliance obligations in the jurisdiction of taxation are limited to what is strictly necessary for the effective collection of the tax while ensuring compliance burdens are proportional to the revenue collected. Appropriate simplification is particularly important to facilitate compliance for businesses faced with obligations in multiple jurisdictions. Where traditional registration and compliance procedures are complex, their application for foreign suppliers of B2C services and intangibles would risk creating barriers that may lead to non-compliance or to certain suppliers declining to serve customers in jurisdictions that impose such burdens.

This chapter provides further guidance and possible options for the design and operation of simplified registration and collection regimes, to support the policy analysis in the jurisdictions that

may consider implementing such a regime or that may be reviewing their existing registration-based regime. It complements Chapter 2, which examines the following key aspects of the design and implementation of a registration-based VAT collection regime: (i) policy considerations informing the decision whether or not to implement a threshold below which foreign suppliers are relieved of the obligation to register, collect and remit the VAT in the taxing jurisdiction; (ii) the possible role of service providers in facilitating foreign suppliers to meet their VAT obligations; (iii) approaches for determining and evidencing the status of the customer (where required); and the customer's location (where required).

This report acknowledges that the design and implementation of a simplified registration and collection regime is likely to differ across jurisdictions, taking into account differences in policy and legislative environments, in administrative practice and culture, and tax authorities' distinct challenges and priorities. In addition, differences in business models and configurations are likely to affect businesses', or business sectors', capacity to comply with specific requirements. This chapter therefore is not intended to present or recommend a one-size-fits-all approach for designing and implementing a simplified regime, but to consider a range of possible options based on countries' experiences in designing and administering their existing regimes and on businesses' experiences in complying with these regimes. The core objective of this chapter is to assist jurisdictions in designing, administering and evaluating their simplified registration and collection regimes with a view to achieving the greatest possible consistency among compliance processes across jurisdictions. Greater consistency among country approaches will further facilitate compliance, particularly by businesses that are faced with multijurisdictional obligations, reduce compliance costs and improve the effectiveness and quality of compliance processes. For tax authorities, consistency is also likely to support the effective international co-operation in tax administration and enforcement.¹

This chapter builds and elaborates on the general description of the possible main features of a simplified registration and collection regime set forth in Section C.3.3 of the Guidelines. It examines in further detail the possible options for the design, administration and practical operation of the following core elements of a simplified registration and collection regime:

- Possible scope of a simplified registration and collection regime.
- Registration.
- Input tax recovery – Refunds.
- Returns.
- Payments.
- Record keeping.

² Guidelines, paragraph 3.132

- Invoicing.
- Availability of information.
- Regularisation of suppliers that have failed to register.
- Lead time for implementation.

Experience shows that consultation with the business community is essential for the design and operation of an efficient and effective simplified registration and collection regime. Such consultations allow tax authorities to acquire a thorough understanding of the business sectors that are likely to be affected, their business models and the role of the various stakeholders in generating and making the supplies likely to fall within the scope of the prospective regime. Such consultation also allows tax authorities to consider the roles and responsibilities of each of these stakeholders in the collection and the remittance of VAT under the simplified regime, and to examine these stakeholders' capabilities in collecting and remitting the VAT and their limitations. These consultations also permit the affected businesses to gain a better understanding of how policy is developed and of tax authorities' policy objectives and constraints. This is likely to enhance businesses' understanding of the regimes and its objectives and to benefit the overall compliance level.

Scope of the simplified registration and collection regime

The Guidelines recommend the simplified registration and collection regime as a solution for the effective collection of VAT on B2C supplies of services and intangibles by a supplier that is not located in the jurisdiction of taxation. This presumes, of course, that this jurisdiction has the taxing rights over these supplies in accordance with the Guidelines for determining the place of taxation (chapter 3 of the Guidelines) and that this jurisdiction decides to exercise these taxing rights. The Guidelines observe that the reverse charge mechanism, which is the recommended solution for B2B supplies of services and intangibles by foreign suppliers, does not offer an effective solution for collecting VAT on B2C supplies.

The Guidelines also recommend that such a simplified registration and collection regime operate separately from the traditional registration and collection regime, without the same rights (e.g. input tax recovery) and obligations (e.g. full reporting) as a traditional regime. Jurisdictions that decide to implement such a simplified regime that operates separately from the traditional regime will need to determine the scope of this simplified regime, i.e. it must determine the categories of supplies for which VAT will be remitted under the simplified regime as distinguished from the other categories for which the traditional regime would continue to apply.

This section examines this question in light of countries' analysis and experiences. Two approaches may be distinguished: a broad approach and a targeted approach.

Broad approach: all B2C supplies of services and intangibles by foreign suppliers in scope

The Guidelines do not limit the potential scope of the simplified registration and collection regime. Such a regime could be used to collect VAT on any type of B2C supply of services and intangibles by a foreign supplier, no matter on what basis (or "proxy") the taxing rights are allocated to the jurisdiction of taxation. The simplified registration and collection regime could thus be used to collect the VAT on any type of B2C supplies by suppliers that are not located in the taxing jurisdiction and for which this jurisdiction has acquired the taxing rights on the basis of any of the place of taxation rules recommended by the Guidelines i

- Guideline 3.5: for supplies that are subject to taxation in the jurisdiction where they are physically performed (e.g. sale of a theatre ticket by a supplier who is not located in the jurisdiction where the theatre performance takes place);

- Guideline 3.6: for supplies that are taxed in the jurisdiction where the customer has its usual residence (e.g. movie downloads);

- Guideline 3.7: for supplies that are subject to a "specific" rule for determining the place of taxation;

- Guideline 3.8: for supplies that are taxed in the jurisdiction where the immovable property is located (e.g. services directly connected with immovable property supplied by a foreign supplier).

The main common feature of the foregoing supplies is that the supplier is not located in the jurisdiction of taxation. The simplified registration and collection regime can provide an efficient and effective solution for collecting the VAT on B2C supplies of services and intangibles by such a foreign supplier. Facilitating compliance for these foreign suppliers is expected to stimulate compliance, thus securing VAT revenue and minimising competitive distortions between domestic and foreign suppliers.

An advantage of such a broad approach is that it reduces risks of uncertainty, complexity and possible disputes that might result from implementing different tax treatments for different categories or types of supplies. It reduces definitional questions (no need to define what is in and what is out of scope); it reduces the need to revise the rules whenever new types of supplies emerge and is therefore likely to be more future proof than a limited approach (which is typically relevant in the digital economy – see below under B.2.); and it is likely to ensure greater consistency in the tax treatment of similar types of supplies. Overall, a broad approach is therefore likely to reduce complexity and uncertainty for suppliers as well as for tax administrations.

On the other hand, tax authorities may wish to choose an approach whereby simplification measures are implemented only for those areas where there is a need for such measures. They may thus wish to avoid reforms, and changes for both suppliers and the tax administration, that may affect areas for which there is no compelling need for change. In the end, it is for the tax authorities to carefully balance both considerations: the potential advantage of implementing a broad approach in

minimising uncertainty with regard to the scope of a simplified regime and minimising risks of uneven treatment between supplies that are in and out of scope; and the potential disadvantage of opening the simplification for supplies and/or suppliers where there is no need to deviate from the traditional registration and collection regime.

Targeted approach: scope limited to specific type(s) of B2C supplies of services and intangibles

A number of jurisdictions have chosen to limit the scope of their simplified registration and collection regime to what can broadly be described as digital B2C supplies by foreign businesses. These typically include the following categories of supplies: digital content purchases (downloads of e-books, videos, apps, games, music); subscription based supplies of content (news, music, streaming of video, online gaming); supplies of software services and maintenance (anti-virus software, digital data storage, etc.); licensing of content (e.g. access to specialised online content such as publications and journals, software, cloud based systems, etc.); and telecommunication and broadcasting services. Such an approach may be motivated by the objective to ensure the effective collection of VAT on B2C supplies in sectors where the risk of competitive distortion between domestic and foreign suppliers is considered most acute and/or where tax revenue is considered to be most at risk.

A distinct tax treatment of supplies depending on their classification (e.g. digital supplies vs. nondigital) is likely to create classification challenges for both tax authorities and suppliers. This is particularly challenging in a digital environment, which is in constant evolution and is characterised by constant innovation leading to continuous changes in business and delivery models and the emergence of new business sectors and new types of services. In such an environment, it is often challenging for a non-expert to understand the key characteristics of a supply and to classify it for VAT purposes as being in or out of the intended scope of the simplified registration and collection regime (e.g. whether or not it is digital). It also requires tax authorities to constantly monitor the digital market evolutions, to ensure that the existing classifications remain updated. The failure to do so may result in revenue losses (as new types of supplies may not be captured) and competitive distortions. This may result in arbitrary distinctions in tax treatment between supplies that may in practice be similar or identical (e.g. whether or not a phone call is carried out over the internet; there may be instances where a supplier or the tax administration cannot even know by which means the call is carried out). These classification challenges are likely to become increasingly difficult for suppliers to manage, as more tax authorities implement simplified registration and collection regimes and different classifications and definitions are implemented across jurisdictions. This would most likely have a negative effect on compliance levels as a result of misclassification and growing complexity confronting suppliers with VAT obligations in multiple jurisdictions in a globalised digital economy.

A separate issue that may arise under a targeted approach is that a one-off supply that is not covered by the simplified registration and collection regime by a supplier that is registered under such a regime may result in an additional obligation for this supplier to register under the traditional regime. This could be addressed by offering the foreign supplier the flexibility to choose to declare such a supply under the simplified regime, under certain conditions (e.g. up to a certain amount). Such flexibility should be carefully considered so as to ensure a proper balance between simplification and the needs of tax administrations to safeguard the revenue through a manageable process.

B.3 Overall considerations on the scope of a simplified registration and collection regime.

Determining the scope of a simplified registration and collection regime requires consideration of a wide range of factors including the existing domestic legal and economic context, the administrative and technical capacities and the constantly changing technological and commercial environment. Both a broad and a targeted approach merit consideration. It is anticipated, however, that a targeted approach may become increasingly difficult to operate over time as new technologies and business models continue to emerge and the types of services that can be supplied remotely to final consumers by foreign suppliers continue to grow.

Whichever approach tax authorities may choose to implement, they are encouraged to give appropriate consideration to the following policy actions:

- To provide clear and easily accessible communication on the supplies that are covered by the regime, in order to maximise certainty for both suppliers and the tax administration;
- To regularly review the efficiency and the effectiveness of the regime, including assessing whether its scope remains fit for purpose.

Against this backdrop, a jurisdiction may, for example opt for a targeted approach with a view to gradually extending the scope of the simplified registration and collection regime as this regime matures, in line with technological and commercial developments.

C. Approaches to organising and simplifying registration and compliance under a simplified regime.

The Guidelines acknowledge that the simplest way to engage with tax administrations from a remote location is most likely through electronic processes,⁴ i.e. registration and compliance processes could be delivered principally through electronic means with minimal requirements for physical movement of documentation. Such an approach can deliver considerable benefits both to tax administrations and to taxpayers. Many tax administrations have indeed taken steps to exploit the opportunities offered by technological innovation to develop a range of electronic processes to support the operation of their simplified registration and collection regimes, including the development of dedicated web portals. The Annex A to this report provides a high-level overview of key features of a simple and easy to use a web portal to facilitate the registration and compliance process.

It is recognised that tax administrations operate in varied environments and reliance on electronic processes may differ depending on the existing infrastructure or capacity. Against this background any reference to electronic processes in the following paragraphs is only intended to serve as a reference point to assist policy makers in their efforts to organise and simplify registration and compliance processes under a simplified regime, taking into account their specific circumstances and practices. 4 Guidelines, paragraph

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